

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS.
PART. XIV. COBALT(IC) AND CHROMIUM METAPHENYLENE.
DIBIGUANIDE COMPLEXES

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Diamminocobaltic *m*-phenylenedibiguanide chloride was prepared by oxidizing with air, a mixture of cobaltous chloride and *m*-phenylenedibiguanide chloride in strong ammonia solution. From the complex chloride the corresponding hydroxide, nitrate and sulphate were obtained. It lost ammonia on heating and gave rise to dichlorocobaltic *m*-phenylenedibiguanide chloride, the latter on hydrolysis gave the corresponding complex diaquo-chloride. Measurement of conductivity indicated slight hydrolysis in aqueous solution even of the complex diammino- and diaquo-chloride. The complex diaquo-hydroxide was also obtained directly from the diammino-chloride by treatment with KOH solution. From the diaquo-base a number of salts, chloride, nitrate and sulphate, was obtained. Treatment of the complex dichloro- and diaquo-chloride with potassium oxalate led only to the formation of a complex diaquo-oxalate, suggesting the *trans*-configuration of these complexes.

Using an excess of *m*-phenylenedibiguanide chloride a dicobaltic *tris-m* phenylenedibiguanide hydroxide was prepared, following the method employed for the preparation of the diammino complex. From this base a number of its salts, chloride nitrate and sulphate, was obtained. These were also found to hydrolyse slightly in aqueous solution.

A bright red cobaltous *m*-phenylenedibiguanide chloride was prepared in the absence of air. Measurement of its magnetic moment value ($\mu_s = 4.34$) proved it to be an ionic or associated complex, differing thus from the covalent cobaltic complexes.

Using chromium in place of cobalt, only a complex of the dichromium *tris*-biguanide type was obtained. The complex hydroxide and its salts, chloride, nitrate and sulphate, have been described here.

Complex compounds of *m*-phenylenedibiguanide with bivalent metals like copper and nickel have been described by Rây and Siddhanta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 200). A study of its complex compounds with trivalent metals like cobalt and chromium forms the subject-matter of the present paper.

As already stated, the *m*-phenylenedibiguanide molecule presents four points of attachment behaving as a quadridentate group, instances of which are rather rare. Therefore, with trivalent metals like cobalt and chromium, in addition to the formation of diammino-, dichloro- and diaquo-biguanide complexes, it has been found that two atoms of the metal may combine with three molecules of *m*-phenylenedibiguanide giving rise to some sort of a bridge compound as represented above.

On treating a solution of cobaltous chloride with that of an equivalent amount of *m*-phenylenedibiguanide chloride, rendered just alkaline with ammonia, a red cobaltous compound is first precipitated, which is slowly oxidized to the cobaltic state with aerial oxidation and passes into solution. The cobaltous *m*-phenylenedibiguanide hydrochloride, unlike many other cobaltous complexes, is a fairly stable substance. It gives a magnetic moment value of $4.3 \mu_B$ which approximates that of cobaltous ion ($4.5 - 5 \mu_B$). The formation of a complex of the ionic or associated type is thereby suggested.

From the oxidation of cobaltous complex in presence of ammonia by air the diammino-cobaltic *m*-phenylenedibiguanidinium chloride was obtained. The corresponding nitrate, sulphate and hydroxide were then prepared from it.

By heating an aqueous alkaline suspension of the diammino-hydroxide on a water-bath till all ammonia was removed, the complex diaquo-hydroxide was prepared. The corresponding salts were then obtained from the base.

The hydrated diammino chloride lost all its water molecules at $85^\circ - 95^\circ$ and then both the ammonia molecules on being heated further to 105° . The intermediate monammino stage could not, however, be realized. The product, dichloro-cobaltic *m*-phenylenedibiguanidinium chloride, was found to be stable only in the solid state. For, on recrystallization from water it gave the complex diaquo-chloride. Similarly, when treated with a solution of potassium oxalate the product gave only an aquo-oxalate. This suggests a *trans* configuration for the diammino, and hence for the dichloro and diaquo complexes, as was expected from a consideration of the fact that the *m*-phenylenedibiguanide normally behaves as a quadridentate molecule.

All the cobaltic complexes, as usual, were found to be diamagnetic. They are thus octahedral complexes of the inner-metallic penetration type with d^2sp^3 hybrid bonds. All the soluble diammino-salts give slightly alkaline solution indicating slight hydrolysis. This is also supported by their conductivity data.

With chromium it has not been possible to prepare the mixed complexes. It gave only the *trans*-biguanide dichromium complex of the bridge configuration.

The solubility of the complex Co^{III} and Cr^{III} compounds, described here, increases in the order: hydroxide $\rightarrow$ sulphate $\rightarrow$ nitrate $\rightarrow$ chloride.

The hydrolysis in the cobaltic series increases in the order: *trans*-Biguanide dicobaltic chloride $\rightarrow$ complex diaquo-chloride $\rightarrow$ complex diammino-chloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *Diammino-cobaltic m-Phenylenedibiguanidinium Chloride*.— *m*-Phenylenediamine dihydrochloride (18.1 g.) and dicyandiamide (16.8 g.) in 100 c.c. of water were

boiled under reflux for 2 to 3 hours; the mixture was then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was mixed with 50 c.c. of liquor ammonia and then a solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (23 g. in the least quantity of water) was added slowly to it with constant stirring. A vigorous current of air was then passed through it for 6 to 8 hours, adding a further quantity of 25 c.c. of strong ammonia after one hour. The solution was then cooled, just neutralized with dilute HCl , and precipitated with absolute alcohol in the cold. Red brown crystals of the substance gradually separated from the solution. There is a tendency for the substance to separate in the form of an oil with rise of temperature. The crystals were washed with alcohol. The product was dissolved in the least quantity of water, acidified with a few drops of HCl , and precipitated again in the cold by alcohol. This was washed first with dilute alcohol, then with absolute alcohol, and finally dried in air. {Found: N, 29.61; Cl, 18.68, 18.70; Co, 10.30, 10.35; H_2O (by loss at 90°), 15.55. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \cdot \text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 29.60; Cl, 18.76; Co, 10.39; H_2O , 15.70 per cent}; where $\text{BigH}_2 = \text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7$.

The substance forms dark brown crystals, highly soluble in water. The solution reacts alkaline to litmus. When heated, it begins to lose water at 80° and is completely dehydrated at 90° . At 100° it begins to lose ammonia, which is completely removed at 105° .

The anhydrous product is very dark and becomes darker grey after deamination. The deaminated product is stable only in the solid state and, on recrystallization, changes to the diaquo-chloride. {Found (for the anhydrous product): N, 35.25; Co, 12.40; NH_3 (by loss at 105°), 7.19. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \cdot \text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 35.18; Co, 12.36; NH_3 , 7.12 per cent}.

{Found for the deaminated product, dichloro cobaltic *m*-phenylenedibiguanidium chloride: N, 31.60; Co, 13.40. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ requires N, 31.60; Co, 13.31 per cent}.

Equivalent conductivity of the complex diammino chloride at 35° .

$v \dots$	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
$\Delta v \dots$	96.7	107.6	116.5	124.2	131.6	136.2	140.6

$$\Delta v = \Delta, (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-1}) \text{ from Walden's formula.}$$

$$\Delta v (\text{mean}) = 148.05 \quad n_1 \text{ and } n_2 \text{ are the valencies of the ions}$$

2. *The Complex Diammino Hydroxide.*—The complex diammino chloride (2 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of water and the solution treated with 10 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The mixture was then strongly cooled in ice, and a concentrated solution of KOH was added to it, drop by drop, with vigorous stirring. A chocolate-brown precipitate was obtained. This was filtered, washed several times at first with cold water, then with absolute alcohol, and finally dried in air, free from carbon dioxide. {Found: N, 31.80; Co, 11.20. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^+)_2 \cdot \text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2](\text{OH})_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 31.70; Co, 11.13 per cent}.

The substance is insoluble in water, but reacts strongly alkaline to moist litmus paper. It loses ammonia on warming with KOH solution forming the complex diaquo-hydroxide. When digested with ammonium chloride solution on the water-bath it dissolves slowly with liberation of ammonia.

3. The *complex diammino sulphate* was prepared by precipitating a solution of the complex diammino chloride with ammonium sulphate. The mixture was kept overnight in the cold. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 27.0; Co, 9.40; SO₄, 23.14. [C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂Co.(NH₃)₂]₂(SO₄)₃.12H₂O requires N, 26.90; Co, 9.44; SO₄, 23.0 per cent}.

The substance forms almost insoluble, chocolate-red crystals with a tendency to turn pasty in water.

4. The *complex diammino nitrate* was obtained from a solution of the complex chloride by precipitation with ammonium nitrate. The rose-red crystalline precipitate was washed with very dilute nitric acid in the cold. The precipitate was dissolved in the least quantity of water and reprecipitated from the solution by the addition of alcohol. The crystals were washed first with ice-cold water, then with absolute alcohol, and dried in air. {Found: N, 29.12; Co, 10.28; NO₃, 32.21. [C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂Co.(NH₃)₂](NO₃)₃.H₂O requires N, 29.20; Co, 10.26; NO₃, 32.28 per cent}.

The substance is moderately soluble in water.

5. *Diaquo-cobaltic m-phenylenedibiguanidinium hydroxide* was obtained by digesting a strong solution of the complex diammino chloride with a concentrated KOH solution on the water-bath till all ammonia was removed. The mixture was cooled, and the product was filtered and heated again with KOH solution on the water-bath. The crystals were washed several times with water, followed by alcohol. These were then dried in CO₂-free air. {Found: N, 31.85; Co, 13.27. [C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂Co.(H₂O)₂](OH)₂.H₂O requires N, 31.75; Co, 13.35 per cent}.

The substance forms pale brown crystals, sparingly soluble in water; it reacts strongly alkaline to moist litmus paper and absorbs CO₂ from air. When heated with a solution of an ammonium salt it liberates ammonia from the latter.

6. The *complex diaquo chloride* was prepared by dissolving the above described hydroxide in an equivalent amount of dilute HCl. The substance was then precipitated from the solution by absolute alcohol. The same product was also obtained from the dichloro cobaltic complex (*vide supra*), when an aqueous solution of the latter was allowed to crystallize. {Found: N, 21.30; Co, 8.98; Cl, 16.14. [C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂Co.(H₂O)₂]₂Cl₂.10H₂O requires N, 21.21; Co, 8.95; Cl, 16.14 per cent}.

The substance forms dark red-brown crystals, readily soluble in water.

Equivalent conductivity at 35°.

$v \dots$	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Δv	90.18	100.3	109.1	117.0	121.9	126.5	130.9

$$\Delta v = \Delta v (1 + 0.692 \times \mu_1 \times \mu_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}}); \quad \Delta v_{(\text{unbound})} = 137.90$$

7. The *complex diaquo sulphate* was obtained by precipitating a solution of the complex diaquo chloride with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate. {Found: N, 21.10; Co, 8.90; SO₄, 21.90. [C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂Co.(H₂O)₂]₂(SO₄)₃.16H₂O requires N, 21.20; Co, 8.94; SO₄, 21.82 per cent}.

The substance forms orange-brown crystals, sparingly soluble in water.

8. The *complex diaquo oxalate* was formed when a solution of the complex diaquo or diammino chloride was treated with a saturated solution of potassium oxalate. The

violet coloured crystalline precipitate was washed and dried as usual. The same product was obtained from the complex diaquo base and oxalic acid. {Found: N, 26.0; Co, 10.90; C₂O₄, 24.50. [C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂.Co.(H₂O)₂]₂(C₂O₄)₃.4H₂O requires N, 25.95; Co, 10.90; C₂O₄, 24.44 per cent}.

9. *Dicobaltic tris-m-Phenylenedibiguanidinium Hydroxide*.—A solution of *m*-phenylenedibiguanidinium chloride, prepared from *m*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride (18.1 g.) and dicyandiamide (16.8 g.) was treated with 50 c.c. of liquor ammonia and a solution of CoCl₂.6H₂O (15 g.) dissolved in the least quantity of water. A vigorous current of air was passed through the mixture for 8 to 10 hours. The dark red solution was then heated on the water-bath till all excess of ammonia escaped. The solution was then diluted to 150 c.c. and was treated with an excess of concentrated KOH solution dropwise in the cold with constant stirring. The dull red precipitate, thus formed, was filtered, washed at first with cold water, then with absolute alcohol, and finally dried in CO₂-free air. This formed the starting material for preparing the other compounds of the series. {Found: N, 34.12; Co, 9.52. [{C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂]₃.Co₂}(OH)₆.10H₂O requires N, 34.04; Co, 9.56 per cent}.

The substance forms insoluble red crystals, which reacts strongly alkaline to moist litmus paper and liberates ammonia from ammonium salts.

10. The *complex dicobaltic sulphate* was prepared by digesting the above described hydroxide with an equivalent amount of warm dilute sulphuric acid. The mixture was diluted with warm water and filtered. The filtrate was left overnight in the cold, when orange-red crystals of the sulphate separated out. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 25.10; Co, 6.95; SO₄, 17.12; H₂O (by loss at 95°), 21.0. [{C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂]₃.Co₂}(SO₄)₃.20H₂O requires N, 25.0; Co, 7.0; SO₄, 17.10; H₂O, 21.43 per cent}. It forms sparingly soluble orange-red crystals.

11. The *complex dicobaltic nitrate* was prepared like the sulphate from the complex hydroxide and dilute nitric acid. It forms chocolate-red crystals, soluble in water. {Found: N, 31.62; Co, 8.89; NO₃, 28.21. [{C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂]₃.Co₂}(NO₃)₆ requires N, 31.72; Co, 8.95; NO₃, 28.10 per cent}.

12. The *complex dicobaltic chloride* was prepared from the complex hydroxide and dilute HCl, following the process described for the previous compound. From the cold solution the crystals of the chloride were precipitated by the addition of alcohol. {Found: N, 28.50; Cl, 14.37; Co, 7.99; [{C₆H₄(BigH⁺)₂]₃.Co₂}Cl₆.13H₂O requires N, 28.47; Cl, 14.44; Co, 8.0 per cent}.

The substance forms brown coloured crystals, readily soluble in water.

Equivalent conductivity at 35°.

<i>v</i> ...	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Δ <i>v</i> ...		99.06	107.7	116.0	120.9	125.1	129.1
Δ <i>v</i> (mean)	=136.2						

13. *m-Phenylenedibiguanide Cobaltous Chloride*.—A solution of a freshly prepared *m*-phenylenedibiguanide hydroxide in a small quantity of air-free ice-cold water was

placed in an atmosphere of hydrogen in the Kapsenberg's filtering apparatus (*vide* this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 163). An almost saturated solution of cobalt chloride (equimolecular amount) in ice-cold, air-free water was added to the previous solution in the filtering apparatus. Cold liquor ammonia (2 c.c.) was then gradually added to the mixture with constant shaking. A brilliant red crystalline precipitate separated out, which was filtered in the apparatus in the hydrogen atmosphere. The crystals were washed in the same apparatus first with previously boiled cold water and then with absolute alcohol. The product was dried in a desiccator filled with hydrogen. {Found: N, 30.30; Cl, 15.22; Co, 12.70. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2\text{Co}]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 30.32; Cl, 15.36; Co, 12.76 per cent}.

The substance forms beautiful vermilion-red crystals, fairly stable in the dry air, but is oxidized and decomposed by moist air.

Magnetic susceptibility of the substance was measured in a Gouy's balance with a field strength of 10.16×10^3 gauss, at 30° .

$\chi_g = 16.11 \times 10^{-8}$; $\chi_M = 7442.8 \times 10^{-6}$; diamagnetic correction = -260.0×10^{-6} ; $\chi_A = 7702.8 \times 10^{-6}$, $\mu_B = 2.84 \sqrt{\chi_A \times T} = 4.34$. The moment value agrees more or less with that of the cobaltous ion.

14. *Dichromium tris-m-Phenylenedibiguanidinium Hydroxide*.—A cold solution of *m*-phenylenedibiguanide hydrochloride in excess was treated with a saturated solution of chrome alum. The mixture was placed on the water-bath and solid KOH was added to it in small portions with stirring. A fine red crystalline precipitate was finally obtained. After cooling, this was filtered, washed first with cold water and then with alcohol. The product was dried in CO_2 -free air. {Found: N, 37.80; Cr, 9.35; H_2O (by loss at 90°), 6.50 [$\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^+)_2\}_3\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 37.75; Cr, 9.35; H_2O , 6.47 per cent}.

The substance forms brilliant rose-red crystals, sparingly soluble in water. It melts when heated on the water-bath, reacts strongly alkaline to litmus paper, and expels ammonia from ammonium salts.

15. *The Complex Dichromium Chloride*.—When the above described hydroxide was digested with a strong solution of ammonium chloride on the water-bath it gradually went into solution with liberation of ammonia. When all the free ammonia was removed, the solution was filtered. On slowly adding cold alcohol to the filtrate, cooled in ice, the crystals of the complex chloride separated from the solution. After keeping the mixture in the cold overnight, the crystals were filtered and washed with absolute alcohol, and then dried in air. {Found: N, 33.75; Cl, 17.06; Cr, 8.29. [$\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^+)_2\}_3\text{Cr}_2\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 33.87; Cl, 17.12; Cr, 8.39 per cent}.

The substance forms highly soluble, rose-red crystals.

16. *The complex dichromium nitrate* was prepared as above by digesting the complex hydroxide with a strong solution of ammonium nitrate on the water-bath. The filtrate, when cooled in ice, deposited light rose-red crystals of the nitrate. These crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 32.10; Cr, 8.0; NO_3 , 28.30. [$\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{BigH}^+)_2\}_3\text{Cr}_2(\text{NO}_3)_6$ requires N, 32.06; Cr, 7.94; NO_3 , 28.40 per cent}.

The substance is fairly soluble in hot water.

17. The *complex dichromium sulphate* was obtained as a precipitate by treating a solution of the complex chloride with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate. It forms very sparingly soluble rose-coloured crystals. {Found : N, 29.50 ; Cr, 7.20 ; SO₄, 20.20. [{C₆H₄ (Big I⁺)₃ }₃.Cr₂](SO₄)₃.11H₂O requires N, 29.49 ; Cr, 7.30 ; SO₄, 20.23 per cent }.

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